

CORRECTION

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Correction: Evolution of important glucosinolates in three common *Brassica* vegetables during their processing into vegetable powder and *in vitro* gastric digestion

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The authors regret that Nan Fu was not included as a corresponding author in the original article. The corrected author list and corresponding authors are as shown above.

The Royal Society of Chemistry apologises for these errors and any consequent inconvenience to authors and readers.

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